

Indonesian EFL Learners' Attitudes and Perceptions on Task-based Language Teaching

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 24, 2025</p> <p>Accepted: June 26, 2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Task-based Language Teaching (TBLT), attitude, perception, Indonesia</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15748164</p>	<p><i>Task-based Language Teaching in Asia, especially Indonesia, was more prevalent in foreign language English teaching. The approach that focuses on the student is seen as more effective than the traditional one. This study was undertaken so as to find out the attitude and perspective of learners regarding implementing language teaching based on tasks (TBLT). Ninety-six learners of the Islamic Junior high school in Indonesia were randomly selected. To investigate participants' attitudes and perceptions, a task-based questionnaire has been designed. By employing the Likert Scale, data were evaluated quantitatively. The study results demonstrate that most EFL Indonesian learners generally have good attitudes and views concerning TBLT, so most of them like to join TBLT English class. In other words, EFL learners are ready to adapt to a new method of language learning because they are willing to apply TBLT successfully. In this study, some major issues highlighted by the results will be examined, and some significant suggestions made by the results are discussed.</i></p>

Introduction

Task-based Language Teaching (TBLT) became widely used in the early 1980s as a second language learning concept to develop a process-based syllabus and design communication tasks that promote the practical use of language by learners with communication skills development. Recent studies show three recurring features among the many interpretations of TBLT concerning classroom practice: (1) TBLT is aligned with a pedagogical philosophy of learners, (2) it incorporates specific elements such as the objective, process and particular results (Skehan, 1998; Murphy, 2003); and (3) it promotes meaningful content-based activities instead of the forms of linguistic (Carless, 2002; Littlewood, 2004).

TBLT is considered an alternative teaching approach as it favours a method that uses functional communicative language (Willis, 1996; Ellis, 2003). According to Ellis (2003) and Willis (1996), TBLT is an efficient approach to create a learning environment that enables students to use target forms of language, which they believe are more likely to reach communicative goals. Moreover, Richards and Rodgers (2014) reported that Task-based Language Teaching was significantly interested in applied linguistics. It has had few actual practical implementations and scant documentation on its impact or efficacy as a basis for designing the curriculum, material development and teaching of classrooms.

Task-based Language Teaching develops a strong understanding of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). It seeks to create a second language linguistic repertoire by enabling learners to participate in a drift of classroom activities (Ellis, 2003 & Richards, 2006;). As a result, language learning results from building appropriate communicative work in the classroom (Richards, 2006), which indicates a form of promoting learner focus, with learners being more involved in the learning process. Furthermore, TBLT concentrates on applying authentic material, language skills, cognitive processes (Ellis, 2003) and promotes meaningful communication in language teaching. During the tasks, the learners can learn more about the target language by reading or listening; this exhibition can assist them to understand the meaning of the language (Willis, 1996).

TBLT studies have grown in varying ways from understandings, opinions and reasons for using TBLT or avoiding its implementation (Bernard and Viet, 2010; Le, 2014). However, in EFL countries, learners have minimal access to English as a target language in daily life. Therefore, "real opportunities must be provided for language use in the classroom" (Jean and Hahn, 2006). In particular, TBLT is still not sufficiently investigated or empirically proved in Indonesia (Hutagalung and Purwati, 2014). In other words, they studied TBLT in EFL contexts, but not in the attitudes and perceptions of EFL learners. The attitude and perception of the student's language teaching process have an enormous impact on what they do.

In the Indonesian EFL context, there have been few empirical studies to study the attitudes and perceptions of language learners. It is, therefore, necessary to investigate the perceptions of learners about TBLT in the Indonesian EFL context, taking into consideration essential roles and attitudes and perceptions in TBLT. TBLT as an alternative approach can be mainly seen in the positive views of the learners. Rifkin (2000) argued that the

learner's attitude in the learning process is essential to determine the failure or success of the learner. Teachers need to know learners' points of view to provide better learning results since this approach has helped or hampered learners in acquiring the target language. Teachers should also be aware of learners' perceptions, but they should also regard them as a decision to choose the right approach to education (Cray & Currie, 1996).

To address this need, the current study aims to examine the attitudes of learners and their perception of TBLT as implemented in the foreign language teaching environment in English. This study presents the general attitudes of learners and their perceptions of TBLT with a questionnaire. The findings will help teachers plan and carry out any genuine communicative tasks and provide insight into what the teachers do base on the Indonesian EFL context where English is a foreign language.

Review of Literature

Researches on Task-based Language Teaching in EFL Contexts

Most of TBLT research was carried in some countries in EFL contexts. Therefore, it has become increasingly interested in recent years, particularly after efforts have met with different degrees of resistance and success (Ellis, 1996). However, the application for Task-based Language Teaching was not problematic in the context of EFL. In countries with standard classes, learners might need to acclimatize themselves to the interactive method of TBLT in a task-based EFL course researched by McDonough and Chaikitmongkol in Thailand in 2007. In the task-based course, learners reported additional grammar training and language forms. They also desired more help and advice from teachers. The objective of task-based language teaching may also be viewed differently. In an EFL three primary class research in Turkey, İlin, İnözü, and Yumru (2007) revealed that their class tasks concentrated on language rather than form and language practice activities. The study teachers knew about the TBLT's objectives yet utilized them towards the end of the language lessons since it was expected.

Ho and Wong (2004) report that west approaches like TBLT may be inconsistent with public demand and conflict in non-western contexts with educational values and traditions. Although there are some problems with TBLT implementation in the EFL context, the research also recognises the advantages of the strategy and observes the overall positive responsiveness of learners. They realize the need for TBLT to promote learners' independence and transferable abilities and offer learners the chance to do English practice (Ho & Wong, 2004). It is also possible for the tasks to be adjusted to examine the teaching of language elements (İlin, İnözü, & Yumru, 2007). The positive results of this research appear to be encouraging; however, further TBLT research is required to produce more definite results within the EFL context.

Learners' Attitude towards TBLT

Attitude is the product of an interactive process that someone answers from the stimulus accepted. This means that the attitude is closely connected to the object after the receiver. Primadi et al. (2006) thus indicated the three aspects of the attitude concept: English attitudes, English-language attitudes and English-language attitudes. The three theoretical assumptions that attitudes in learning a target language may affect linguistic motivation and can mediate the link between linguistic attitudes and language accomplishments are based on these three attitudes.

Research on attitudes of learners in second language acquisition has been conducted in particular. Gardner (1985) examined individual differences in the language learning process in the context of the socio-educational model. The attitude and motivation of language have been recognized as critical aspects of the learning process since they can encourage active involvement in learning and impact behaviour. He further suggested that learners' attitudes impact their motivation, enhancing the motivation of practices with a good attitude towards language acquisition and vice versa.

Learners play a crucial role in class and learning and can determine the success of TBLT (Chung & Huang, 2009). Understanding their attitudes, beliefs, assumptions, choices and needs is unavoidable if EFL teaching gives language and cultural empowerment to learners (Savignon, 2007). To help learners achieve these goals, a clear understanding of TBLT's attitudes and perceptions as a broad framework for shaping existing definitions of EFL teaching targets is vital (Savignon & Wang, 2003). Exploring student attitudes can therefore lead to better results in language learning. The learners' attitude towards TBLT impacts TBLT, which makes it essential for the learners to implement the TBLT in the classroom. The learners' attitudes are therefore necessary. The discrepancy between TBLT theory and practice may be learners' attitudes; accordingly, as mentioned in Karavas-Doukas (1995), the study of their attitudes serves as the basis for identifying possible contradictions between the beliefs of learners and the principles of TBLT (Chang, 2011).

Studies Exploring Learners' Perception About TBLT

A number of studies focus on the learners' perception of TBLT, but several commonalities exist in these studies. In their study, Meng and Cheng (2010) found that most Chinese learners were excited about and

thought the approach to the task was functional. Learners were excited about the various tasks and believed that this was good because the greater the participation in the task, the better the performance was assessed. However, over a quarter of the participants felt disappointed by their work. Teachers were advised to introduce the task as soon as possible and give learners time to prepare for the job performance. Furthermore, teachers still had to guide learners in their work phases when they were experiencing difficulties. During the activity and after the activity, the teacher plays a crucial role.

The learners' views on TBLT have been studied similarly by Hadi, 2012. In open questionnaires, he studied 88 Iranian female learners. The results show that the learners were positive and welcomed the new TBLT experience. The learners consider that TBLT has offered them the opportunity to cooperate, interact spontaneously, and emphasise their motivating potential with the usage of the target language. Huang (2015) showed positive reactions to TBLT among ELT learners. This study showed that TBLT engaged learners and expanded their interests, and made them more self-reliant. The learners said TBLT enhanced their interest in learning the target language and increased their autonomy by participating actively in preparing the task and improving their searching capacity for information on information gap activities. Learners in nature are never limited to welcoming a new learning experience. Teachers ought to be sensitive to this. It is not easy to create a stage where learners are concerned and committed to learning. Teachers may combine TBLT and traditional teaching.

In Indonesian contexts like several other Asian countries, learners have internet access, and that's how they get excited. Teachers should understand what learners in their real-life usually love and relate to reading activities. For example, Tahririan and Basiri conducted a study on enhancing learners' understanding of reading within TBLT (2005). They both used internet reading as their primary task. The research findings have shown that reading skills such as skimming and scanning are essential for reading on the Internet. Every word or line of the page did not read by the learners. In search of relevant information, they turned their eyes from one item to another.

Context: Issues with TBLT in Indonesia

In the Indonesian context, specific recommendations must be taken into account while implementing TBLT in the English as a foreign language classroom. They concern current curricula and textbooks, demand for a system of evaluation, teachers' beliefs, and objective language use (Fahrurrazy, 2000).

First, the current curriculum of the texts available was not designed using an approach based on the task. However, because the task-orientated approach concerns teaching and learning activities, teachers can modify their lesson readiness to adopt the task-oriented approach with little creativity.

Secondly, applying the task-based strategy will confront a problem with the evaluation system demand. Because it focuses on what the learners are doing rather than what they say, the assessment focuses not on the need for the current language accuracy evaluation system. Teachers are currently encouraged to apply the approach gradually and combine it with teaching and learning activities based on the evaluation system's requests. However, the approach can be fully implemented at the primary school level because English is a subject for local content, so the student assessment is determined not by the external examination but by EFL teachers themselves.

Thirdly, the EFL teachers in Indonesia can believe in their teaching practices. The teachers may believe that they are "not teaching" unless they teach graphics in their traditional ways (e.g. grammar explanation and mechanical drills). Such a belief has to be revised over the long term. Teachers need to develop and update teaching and learning approaches, methods, and techniques.

Fourthly, two things have to be considered for the use of the target language. On the one hand, teachers face a challenge to improve their English skills so that teachers can respond to the need to use their target language. However, beginning EFL learners can be challenged if the teacher only uses English in the classroom (the target language). Prabhu (1984) suggests that other communication resources (such as guessing, gesture, native language or actions) may be used to resolve learners' problems because of the limited mastery of languages. It is a choice to use the native language in a foreign language situation.

Research Methodology

Research Questions

The objective of the study is to explore Indonesian English learners' attitudes toward TBLT. It is also intended to investigate the learners' perception of the learning approach. The following questions have been formulated for this purpose: (1) What are the Indonesian EFL learners' attitudes toward TBLT?, (2) What are the Indonesian English learners' perceptions on the implementation of TBLT?, and (3) Why do English learners in Indonesia like, or dislike the implementation of TBLT?

Research Context

This case study was done at MTsN 3 Demak, a large, public Islamic Junior High School in Demak (Central Java, Indonesia), which requires learners to attend four integrated EFL classes. These learners are subject to the four skills that the EFL curriculum covers and it is called the 2013 curriculum. All of Indonesia's schools have this kind of curriculum. This is why all EFL teachers must participate in the EFL curriculum implementation. TBLT and CLT are the most essential issues for junior and secondary schools across Indonesia after decades of different methods or approaches to English teaching. The present study was carried out with teachers at the Islamic junior high school in EFL teaching.

Research Design

The current study used a survey research design to provide learners at MTsN 3 Demak school with a questionnaire to gather their opinions about their attitude and the perception of Task-based Language Teaching implemented at school.

Participants

The questionnaires included 96 English language learners studying in MTsN 3 Demak school (Central Java, Indonesia). These learners were selected from the teacher's three English classes, and they have different linguistic levels, including lower, median and above-average and advanced levels. The learners are between 12 and 15 years old.

Instruments

The learners' attitude and perception of TBLT in this school have been measured by using a questionnaire. This questionnaire was adapted from Jeon and Hahn (2006). It was written in Indonesian (bahasa Indonesia) so that the learners could understand the content of the questionnaire. It comprised several items of Likert and two open-ended items. It was composed of four parts. A series of questions pertaining to age and gender comprised the first part of the questionnaire. The second part offered learners questions to acquire insight into their preferred English language tasks. The third section attempted to find opinions on TBLT practice in the classroom. The second and third parts requested learners to reply in five points to each issue. Thus, the fourth part explains why they were willing or reluctant to apply for TBLT.

Data Collection

The questionnaires were distributed by an online survey platform (google forms, in Indonesia) to 96 participants from the eighth-grade students of MTsN 3 Demak school to prevent and curbed COVID-19 spread. The participants were requested to fill out the questionnaire and were assured of confidentiality in the information provided. The attitude and perceptions of the learners were gathered by evaluating their answers to the questionnaires.

Data Analysis

The analytical data process was carried out in two steps: (1) the numerical scores were provided for the elements of Likert-specific questionnaires (strongly disagree =1, disagree =2, neutral=3, agree=4, and strongly agree=5), and two for the open end items. Participants were required to decide for or against TBLT for their reasons. For the convenience of data analysis, the selected items had the number score of "1" and the unselected items "0."

In the data analysis, version 21.0 of the Statistical Social Sciences Package (SPSS) was used. A percentage analysis of student answers for each questionnaire was carried out, so as to find out the learners' attitudes and perceptions of TBLT and its implementation in language schools.

Findings

Indonesian EFL learners' attitudes toward TBLT

The quantitative results of the research show that learners at MTsN 3 Demak school have a positive attitude to TBLT.

Table 1. The results of the learners' answers to Section 2 (N=96)

Questionnaire Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	10	9.60	50	48.00	16	15.36	3	2.88	0	0
2	25	24.00	52	49.92	15	14.40	2	1.92	0	0
3	15	14.40	43	41.28	20	19.20	7	6.72	1	0.96
4	10	9.60	35	33.60	22	21.12	9	8.64	2	1.92
5	16	15.36	47	45.12	18	17.28	6	5.76	1	0.96

6	20	19.20	48	46.08	16	15.36	4	3.84	0	0
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Table 1 reveals that most learners agree with the items in general and do not disagree significantly. For the first item: "I enjoy the opportunity of communication through various types of tasks" 9.60% (10 learners) agreed strongly and 48.00% (50 learners) agreed just now, 15.36% (16 learners) were neutral, 2.88% (3 learners) disagreed, and no learners strongly disagreed. Two "English class Task Performances is fun for me." were strongly agreed 24.00 percent (25 learners), 49.92% (52 pupils) were united, 14.40% (15 learners) were neutral, 1.92% (2 learners) were disagreeable and 0% (0 learners) were strongly unanimous. With regard to item Three "Tasks that help myself to engage in spontaneous interactions with English," 14.50 percent (15 learners) agree strongly, 41.28 percent (43 learners) agree, 19.20 percent (20 learners) are neutral, 6.72 percent (7 learners) disagree and 0.96 percent (1 learner) strongly disagree. For item 4, 'Task performances in a classroom prepares me for real-world communications challenges': 9.60 percent (10 learners) were strongly supported, 33.69% (35 learners) agreed, 21.12% (22 learners) showed neutrality, 8.64% (9 learners) were neutral; (35 learners) showed strong support. As with item 5, "Task is a powerful means of facilitating my communication skills in English." 15% (16 learners) strongly agreed, 45% (47 learners) agreed, 17.28% (18 learners) did not agree, 5.76% (6 learners) were united and 0.96% (1 learner) were stringent. " (1 learner) "Task is an effective means of facilitating my communication skills in English." In light of the final point (Item 6 "tasks helping me use expressions and grammar patterns that I've learned"), 19.20% (20 learners) strongly agreed, 46.08% (48 learners) agreed, 15.360% (16 learners) were neutral, 3.84% (4 learners) disagreed with each other, and 0,00% (16 learners) were not in favour.

Indonesian EFL learners' perception on the implementation of TBLT

Section 3 of the questionnaire consisted of eight items that were directly related to the question. The results of the questionnaire responses from learners are displayed in table 2.

Table 2. The Results of the Learners' Responses in Section Three (total 96)

Questionnaire Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
7	30	28.80	49	47.04	10	9.60	3	2.88	0	0
8	22	21.12	55	52.80	12	11.52	2	1.92	0	0
9	27	25.92	50	48.00	13	12.48	4	3.84	12	0.96
10	5	4.80	18	17.28	22	21.12	38	36.48	8	11.52
11	8	7.68	15	14.40	24	23.04	40	38.40	10	7.68
12	10	9.60	18	17.28	18	17.28	36	34.56	0	9.60
13	20	19.20	59	55.68	10	9.60	5	4.80	0	0
14	20	19.20	50	48.00	16	15.36	8	7.68	0	0
15	18	17.28	54	51.84	18	17.28	5	4.80	0	0

Responding to item 7, 28.80% (30 learners) and 47.04% (49 learners) think TBLT is a relaxing learning environment suitable for TBLT promoters in Indonesia. For item 8, 21.12% (22 learners) are firmly in agreement and agree that a collaborative learning environment is created, whereas 5 disagree strongly with this issue or are neutral. As regards Item 9, 25.92% (27 learners) strongly agree with the development of integrated skills in a classroom, and 48.00% or 50 learners agree. 12.48% or 13 learners do not agree with this issue, however, and 4 of the learners (3.84%), so no learners feel very different. 36.48 percent (38 learners) reported that TBLT does not deal with their grammar and 38.40 percent (40 learners) therefore believe that the TBLT is not suited for learners preparing examinations. The answer to item 12 indicates that, even if the student's English is not fluent and accurate, 34.56 or 36 learners think they can do a job well. This shows their trust and interest and also in performing class tasks. 55.68% of learners reported that TBLT was not suitable for the management of classrooms. Therefore 48.00% or 50 learners considered that the responses for items 13 and 14 were not valuable in large classes. The majority of learners (76,7% and 17,28%) agree that TBLT materials are meaningful and purposeful and have a collection of accurate words.

The reasons of Indonesian EFL learners like, or dislike the implementation of TBLT

This section responds to the third question from the research: Why do English learners in Indonesia like or dislike the implementation of TBLT?. The learners can only choose "Yes" or "No" for this section. They had to select one or all five reasons to answer 'yes', but they did have six reasons to choose from if they replied 'no.' Table 3 shows how many reasons learners chose to benefit TBLT, and Table 4 shows the numbers of reasons learners have chosen to dislike TBLT.

Table 3. Reasons why English learners like the implementation of TBLT (N=96)

Reason No.	Learner number	Percentage (learner number/N) (%)
1	34	32.64
2	70	67.20
3	56	53.76
4	78	74.88
5	85	81.60

According to Table 3, only 32,64 percent of the "yes" votes received by reason 1 TBLT were supported by learners' academic advancement, a relatively smaller percentage. Most learners may consider "scholastically progress" in a restricted sense as an accomplishment in examinations, or they cannot rely heavily on TBLT to promote their language skills other than developing communication skills. Reason 2 TBLT improvement attracted 67, 20% of learners' interaction skills, whilst Reason 3 TBLT stimulates 53,76% of learners' 'yes' votes. Reason 4 TBLT develops a collaborative learning environment that attracted 74,88% of learners, showing that their study setting in which communication may take place was given considerable attention. Lastly, 81,60 percent of learners have attracted the reason 5 " TBLT is best used in a small group setting". Table 4 shows the number of reasons for learners who have chosen 'No' option.

Table 4. Reasons why English learners dislike the implementation of TBLT (N=96)

Reason No.	Learner number	Percentage (learner number/N) (%)
1	62	59.52
2	50	48.00
3	75	72.00
4	60	57.60
5	30	28.80

According to Table 4, 59.52 percent of learners decided to choose the reason 1, "Learners are not used to Task-based Language Teaching", 48.00 percent chose reason 2, "The materials in the textbook are not suitable for applying TBLT.", 72.00 percent chose reason 3, "A high-class size makes task-based approaches difficult to employ.", 57.60 percent chose reason 4, "I find my own performance difficult to assess.", and 28.80 percent chose reason 5, "Teachers are not very familiar with TBLT".

Discussion

In response to the first research question, analysis of 1-6 items revealed that learners had a favourable attitude about learning English utilizing the Task-based Language Teaching (TBLT) approach. They were able to communicate information through several sorts of teaching and learning tasks. They realized that the TBLT technique enabled them to strengthen their English communicative abilities. This is shown well in Jeon's (2005) study, which shows that it can be the outcome of the change from the Asian EFL environment towards using task- and activities-based language learning to improve the teaching skills of learners.

With respect to the second question of research examining the perspectives of learners about the implementation of TBLT, the analysis of items 7 to 15 revealed that Indonesian EFL learners had a good attitude regarding the implementation of language classrooms. They were ready to adjust to the new language learning approach. TBLT presents a new languages strategy that is very distinct from the typical PPP paradigm. The changing approach to education creates major issues in the classroom management. The CLT and TBLT concerns with the classroom management system are noted by Littlewood (2007). The familiar 'PPP' sequence offers a technique that "deliver" the language required in the curriculum and a means of controlling class interaction. Many teachers express concern that this control is no longer working when learners participate in independent tasks.

The research findings show that while the learners' attitude regarding the implementation of TBLT, but there is still doubt that it will be effective for grammar and exam preparation. The implication of this finding is also that most of these students believe in traditional teaching that grammar and learning for examinations are key elements in the learning of languages. The findings are consistent with Deng & Carless (2010) and Littlewood (2007), who argue that exams in schools such as communicative or task-based approach are typically viewed to be a barrier to their implementation. While tasks allow students to select a language to get the result of the task, students can choose the elements of grammar to use. The research findings also show that, while learners generally support the TBLT, they remain unconfident of the function of TBLT in grammar and exams. This conclusion also implies that most of these learners believe that grammar and learning for tests are key to language acquisition. The results were consistent with Deng & Carless (2010) and Littlewood (2007), claiming that tests in schools, such as communication and task-based techniques, were commonly perceived as obstacles to their implementation. While tasks enable the learners to select the required language for the task to achieve, and learners can choose which grammar elements to employ, tasks cannot fulfil this requirement.

In answer to the third question of the research, which explains why learners like or dislike the use of TBLT. The results show that learners' motivations for their desire to apply TBLT vary. The majority of learners favoured a task-based approach because they first favoured their cooperation and their interaction and their motivation potential. Although many learners appreciated TBLT due to its adequacy for small groups, this is why TBLT was motivated.

Very few learners have expressed dislike of TBLT. The main reason why they don't like it is that huge class sizes are a barrier to TBLT. In large courses, management can be an issue, according to their reports. If we consider that the size of the English class is generally very large in Indonesia, it is worth talking about this in the future. The second major issue is that they are not used to teaching in a learner-centred classroom in which they find it hard to accomplish chores alone. This outcome is not surprising because Indonesia has long been a teacher-centred language class. Learners have also claimed that evaluating task performance is challenging, which shows that Indonesian learners are used to conventional assessments. The way to assess task performance is, of course, also an issue for teachers.

Conclusion

Studies of the attitude and perception of learners towards task-based language teaching are still limited in the Indonesian context. This research is, therefore, necessary since it takes learners to the front. From the learners' perspective, this research addresses numerous significant TBLT difficulties. Results demonstrate that most Indonesian EFL learners usually have favourable views and perceptions of TBLT; hence most learners enjoy TBLT. Language challenges in TBLT can be of great assistance for creating an exciting environment in which learners enhance their communication skills. This task provides varied language teaching approaches and makes the classroom considerably more enjoyable and engaging; it may also establish a dynamic and creative atmosphere in the classroom that offers language education. Although most learners in Indonesia welcome TBLT, there are still many problems revealed by the research, which are among the significant concern of Indonesian learners concerning the class size, class management, the development of the language grammar of learners, the preparation for examinations and their belief in language learning. Attitudes and perceptions of learners are essential to the success of language teaching. Thus, language teachers in Indonesia should take their attitudes and perceptions carefully.

Regarding the study results, teachers, learners and decision-makers are offered some notifying recommendations. Firstly, since the learners' opinions have a significant impact on their learning process, they must maintain a positive attitude to the TBLT to obtain the intended result. Secondly, because lack of confidence is one reason for learners to avoid TBLT, overcoming those obstacles in the classroom should be considered. Moreover, given that Indonesian EFL learners' attitudes against TBLT were relatively good in this study, EFL teachers are urged to use this approach. In this respect, decision-makers in charge of the school system must also adjust their attitudes and do everything they can to support TBLT.

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